

DESIGN AND TESTING OF A GRAPHITE COMPOSITE RING STIFFENED THERMOSET CYLINDER SUBJECTED TO HYDROSTATIC LOADING

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the numerous steps in the design development of a four foot (1,22m) diameter, AS4/LRF571, graphite/epoxy composite cylindrical model. The cylinder was fabricated by an automated filament winding process and was non-autoclave cured in an oven. The paper reviews the details of the design/analysis approach and assumed failure criteria using 2-D solid axisymmetric finite element analyses with the ABAQUS code. Numerous design iterations were made to achieve a balanced design. The model is composed of 50% circumferential, 33% longitudinal and 17% helical plies, and the ring (blade) stiffener is composed of all circumferential plies. This paper also reviews the assumed material properties used for the design and analyses, and the "as-fabricated" material properties used to predict failure of the cylinder due to hydrostatic loading. The final design achieved a weight savings of 44% over an equivalent steel stiffened cylinder. The cylindrical model was then subjected to a hydrostatic collapse test. A comparison of the test results and the failure prediction is also presented. This work was sponsored by the Maritime Systems Technology Office, Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency.

Key words: Composite Models, Composites Fabrication, Graphite/Epoxy, Hydrostatic Tests, Stiffened Cylinders.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The Maritime Systems Technology Office of the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) implemented a Thick Composite Technology Development for a Man-Rated Demonstration Article (MRDA) Program to develop the technologies, experience and confidence needed to exploit the benefits and potentials of composite materials for submersible structures and components through the transfer of proven aerospace technology. An interactive three phase program was established to develop reliable, cost effective, and proven construction capabilities for a full scale, thick section MRDA. This program progresses from the design, fabrication and testing of subscale composite models to the design, fabrication and testing of a full scale proof-of-concept demonstration article. The first phase of the program includes the design, fabrication, testing and evaluation of a number of 1,22m (48 in) diameter model spheres and stiffened cylinders. These models are required to validate the design procedures, as well as, material fabrication and inspection procedures.

For the first series of tests, a 1,22m (48 in) diameter, thermoset composite cylinder was designed by General Dynamics/Electric Boat Division; fabricated by Brunswick Defense using AS4/LRF-571; Non-Destructively Inspected (NDI) by Brunswick and General Dynamics/Fort Worth Division; and hydrostatically tested. This paper discusses the test results and provides an interpretation of these test results and the failure mechanism.

2.0 DESIGN

The selected controlling dimensions of the stiffened cylinder were a 1,22m (48 in) inside diameter for the cylinder and a minimum 1,09m (43 in) clear bore diameter for the stiffeners. Both thermoset and thermoplastic materials were considered for the cylindrical models. Candidate materials were AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy for the thermoset cylinders and AS4/PEEK for the graphite thermoplastic cylinders. The models were designed for a hydrostatic pressure of 153 bar (2234 psi). A blade stiffened design was selected to accommodate the filament winding fabrication process.

Preliminary sizing of the model was performed using traditional semi-empirical procedures. Detailed design was performed using axisymmetric, nonlinear finite element analyses with ABAQUS (1). For all of the 2D axisymmetric solid ABAQUS analyses, the 3D material properties were determined by the commonly accepted 3D laminate theory of C.T. SUN (2). The material allowables for the design of the model were obtained by utilizing knockdowns to account for thickness, environment, curvature, decreased fiber volume, possible increased porosity, and notched sensitivity. Based on aerospace experience, an allowable through thickness compressive strain of 0.004200 mm/mm (in/in) was selected for AS4/3501-6. Localized higher bending compressive strains were permitted if less than the unnotched laminate compressive strain for AS4/3501-6. To preclude elastic general instability collapse, interframe buckling or local frame tripping of the model, higher margins of stability on these modes of failure were imposed on the model.

Another important design feature of the model was the design of the test end closures and cylindrical end bays in the vicinity of the end closure. Traditional flat plate aluminum test end caps were initially investigated which produced high localized strains in the hull near the end cap. Due to continued concern about this localized condition leading to premature failure, steel spherical end caps were considered and selected to improved compatibility. The discontinuity arising from steel hemispherical closure head produced localized high strains at the end and over the first stiffener (commonly designated as end bay) near the closure head. To produce a more typical hull response and reduce the high bending strains in the end bay, the hull thickness was increased from the first stiffener to the beginning of the hull or over the end bay as shown in Figures 1 and 2. Figure 1 shows the final details of the model with 21,6mm (0.85 in) hull thickness, 127 mm (5 in) frame spacing and 31,8mm (1.25 in) end bay thickness. Figure 2 shows the deformed shape of the thermoset model from the 2D axisymmetric ABAQUS analysis. Maximum through thickness compressive strains of -0,004200 mm/mm (in/in) in the longitudinal direction and of -0,004300 mm/mm (in/in) in the circumferential direction with a localized high compressive strain of -0,004750 mm/mm (in/in) were calculated. Figure 3 shows the typical resultant strain plot for the longitudinal strains at 153 bar (2234 psi).

3.0 FABRICATION

Brunswick Defense was contracted by GD/Electric Boat Division to fabricate the model by filament winding graphite epoxy using Hercules' AS4, 12K fiber, prepregged with 3501-6 resin. However, due to material difficulties, an equivalent Brunswick resin system, LRF-0571, which did not require an MDA curing agent nor autoclave cure was recommended by Brunswick and used for the model. The resin properties also allow for prepregging and B-staging and partially gelling the resin during the winding process. The gel-as-you-wind method provides a firm substrate as the outer layers are applied to minimize fiber wrinkling in the cured

composite. To improve manufacturing and eliminate hand layup of longitudinal mats, only circumferential or hoop ply layups were used for the built-up region. However, based on nonlinear analyses, the total hull thickness was increased to 34mm (1.35 in) from 32mm (1.25 in), or 13mm (0.5 in) of all hoop plies.

A soluble sand mandrel was used for fabrication of the Brunswick hull model to minimize costs without sacrificing dimensional stability. The sand mandrel was fabricated with hemispherical domes at each end to facilitate filament winding of off-axis plies. The domes maintain a stable winding path and prevent intraply gapping of the fiber band which can occur if only pin rings are used for turnarounds. The close tolerances required for the rib stiffeners were achieved by inserting graphite winding channels with precise widths into the sand mandrel. A computer-controlled 7-axis Brunswick filament winder was required to fabricate the composite hull model with a maximum two degree fiber misalignment to the specified hull layup of $[90_2/0_2/90/45/-45/90/0_2/90_2]_{ns}$. The combination of axial and hoop plies in each sublaminate provided the necessary reinforcement to resist the hydrostatic pressure. The off-axis $[\pm 45$ degree] plies provided impact resistance and balance of the in-plane mechanical properties of the hull.

Figure 4 shows the winding of the 45 degree prepreg. After winding, the ends were cut to remove windings over the domes. The cylinder was covered with release cloth, perforated FEP film and duck cloth and wrapped with four plies of Kevlar roving to provide compaction. The cylinder was then oven cured.

After the conducting visual and dimensional inspection to satisfy the fabrication requirements, the model was Non-Destructively Evaluated (NDE) using through Transmission (T-T) and Pulse-Echo (P/E) ultrasonic techniques to determine structural integrity of the model at Brunswick Defense Marion Facility and General Dynamics/Fort Worth Division. NDE inspection showed no large delaminations or voids in the cylinder or stiffeners. High ultrasonic attenuation of the part was observed with the end bays showing the most attenuation which was attributed to higher porosity (4% - 5% vs 1% for autoclaved parts). The end bay regions also had ply drop-offs and different layups than midbay regions resulting in more signal scatter. All circularity readings obtained showed the model to be almost perfectly circular. However, the four plies of Kevlar roving wrapped to provide compaction during final cure resulted in an outer surface wrinkle about 1.5mm (.06 in) high by about 35mm (0.20 inch) wide along the entire length of the cylinder.

4.0 FAILURE ANALYSIS AND PREDICTIONS

The finite element analysis results were employed to predict failure of the cylinder using maximum stress and strain allowables, as well as, a modified Hashin's failure criteria (3). Nodal strains from the FEA were also used to predict strain versus load behavior in order to track the actual strain gauge readings, and to support the post-test failure analysis. Since no coupons were available from the actual cylinder to determine the strength/quality of the cylinder, flat panels fabricated with the same material and layup, and cured at the same time were used. Material properties data were determined by Brunswick Defense and Touchstone Research Laboratory.

The cylinder was modeled using ABAQUS axisymmetric QUAD4 elements with reduced integration and with half-model symmetry. Pre- and post-processing was performed using PATRAN. The final half-models reflected as-built dimensions, more detailed modeling of the blade fillet region, and greater mesh refinements. Three essentially identical FE models were analyzed using three different material property inputs; i.e., Brunswick, Touchstone, and AS4/3501-6 baseline. The models predicted failure to initiate on the inside of the hull near the cap lip. Failure away from the end was predicted at higher loads as shown in Figure 5.

5.0 HYDROSTATIC TESTS

A hydrostatic test was conducted with the ends of the cylinder fitted with two hemispherical steel caps. The caps were tightened with sixteen threaded rods which ran along the outside of the cylinders from cap to cap. The cylinder was fitted with 146 strain gages and acoustic emission devices. Figure 6 shows the inside of the model. All gages were zeroed before testing began with only one gage not operational at the start of the testing. The hydrostatic test consisted of three conditioning tests and a collapse test. Strain gage readings were taken at each increment of pressure after holding the load for five minutes. This allows the gages to reach steady state values before being recorded. After unloading, the cylinder was held at 3,4 bar (50 psi) to ensure that the caps remained seated on the cylinder. Upon conclusion of the three conditioning tests, the cylinder was loaded to collapse. The model suffered catastrophic failure at 124 bar (1800 psi) after being held for two minutes. Figure 7 shows the model after it was removed from the test chamber. A large longitudinal crack running the length of the cylinder can be seen.

6.0 TEST RESULTS AND EVALUATION

Strain gages and acoustic emission were carefully monitored. Linear strain gage response was noted during the first loading and unloading cycle. During the second conditioning cycle, an audible pop was heard and recorded by acoustic emission after holding the pressure at 92 bar (1333 psi). Strain gage data in the vicinity of the end bays on the unloading of the second cycle and loading of the third cycle showed a shift in behavior suggesting partial failure. This observation is consistent with the failed cylinder which showed delamination and cracking of the hoop overwraps in the end bays as noted in Figure 8. Further evidence which indicates that the hoop overwraps broke on both ends during testing was observed from a comparison of the internal and external circumferential and longitudinal strains along the cylinder. Plots of these strains clearly show a major load redistribution in the regions around the first couple of frames on each end.

Review of all of the strain gage responses revealed that a progressive failure of the end bay overwrap segments began during the second load cycle. As the loading cycles continued more failure occurred. The shift in the load versus strain behavior appears to have started closest to the wrinkle and progressed circumferential outward. In general, the shift in response was only exhibited from the second frame on either side and outward in the center. Although this is the likely failure scenario, it does not explain why the overwraps failed at such a low strain level except that high porosity was noted.

To determine the effect of the overwraps, a post-test analysis was performed assuming that there were no overwraps on each end which showed the load redistribution during the test to be consistent with the analysis results. When compared to the failure predicted with the overwraps there is a 12% drop in the failure pressure to 135 bar (1950 psi). The knockdowns used to get the design allowables included some significant conservatism to account for defects and fabrication variations, and the full strength of a good quality cylinder would be expected to be considerably higher. However, the analysis suggested that the cylinder could have reached at least an 8% higher pressure if the overwrap had failed.

Strain gages also showed acceptable strain levels. Longitudinal strains at collapse pressure were about $-0,0027$ mm/mm (in/in) on the inside surface and about $-0,0035$ mm/mm (in/in) on outside surface of the cylinder. The only place where strains were higher was in the triaxial gages in the stiffener to cylinder radius region. Selected strain gage plots from these regions are shown in Figures 9, 10 and 11. The longitudinal strains from these triaxial gages are higher than in other locations (around $-0,0050$ to $-0,0060$ mm/mm, (in/in)). The circumferential strains are about the same magnitude.

Eventhough the overwraps clearly failed, their failure at such low strain levels, -0.0012 and -0.0015 mm/mm (in/in) for the circumferential and longitudinal strains, respectively, was unexpected. Careful inspection of the ultrasonic C-scan of the entire cylinder clearly shows the longitudinal wrinkle which continues from the hull into the taper with the build up of hoop plies. There also is a longitudinal indentation next to the wrinkle. This suggests that the wrinkle and indentation played a major role in the failure of the hoop overwraps and overall failure of the model.

The effect of the longitudinal wrinkle or layer waviness in the hydrostatic collapse of thick composite cylinders has been investigated by Brown and Hyer (4). This reference presents a parametric investigation to determine the combined influence of wave location, wave amplitude and cylinder geometry on the hydrostatic response of the cylinder. For the case with the wave on the outer surface of similar characteristics, strength reduction of about 30% for unstiffened cylinders and about 50% higher strains in the wavy region might be expected. This suggests that large fiber waviness or wrinkles have an effect on the hydrostatic collapse pressure of the model and could account for the further reduction in strength. Failure of the model along this wrinkle or a stress riser can attest to its effect as shown in Figure 7.

7.0 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Although the cylinder did not achieve the desired failure pressure it did provide considerable valuable information and milestones. The blade stiffened cylinder was one of the largest composite cylinders ever tested in hydrostatic compression. A cost-effective, automated, out-of-autoclave, thermoset fabrication process and tooling was demonstrated. This process is scaleable to larger diameters where the cost-effectiveness of the non-vacuum bag and out-of-autoclave process for thick composites is imperative. Although the quality of the cylinder was less than required for a man-rated application, the cylinder reached more than 75% of the predicted failure and provides some assurances that, if quality were improved, the collapse failure load could have been reached. The failure of the hoop overwraps and the wrinkle caused by the shrink wrap are defects which clearly should be avoided in the future. The effects of porosity on both the quality and degradation of the model and interpretation of the NDE ultrasonic inspections results deserve further study. These areas as well as toxicity, flammability, durability, damage tolerance, repair and the effects of marine environment are being evaluated. In-situ consolidated, graphite thermoplastic, stiffened cylinder pressure hull models are being fabricated and will be tested in 1993 to provide the technical knowledge base and confidence level required for future man-rated application.

8.0 REFERENCES

1. Hibbitt, Karlsson & Sorensen, Inc., ABAQUS Version 4.9, General Finite Element Program, Providence, R.I.
2. Sun, C.T., Li, S., "Three-Dimensional Effective Elastic Constants for Thick Laminates", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 22, July 1988.
3. Hashin, Z., "Failure Criteria for Unidirectional Fiber Composites", Journal of Applied Mechanics, June 1980, pp 329-334
4. Hyer, M.W., and Brown, T.L., "Influence of Layer Waviness on the Hydrostatic Response of Thick Composite Cylinders", Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, CCMS-92-21, VPI-E-92-17, July 1992.

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Figure 1 - Thermoset Blade Stiffened Cylinder

Figure 2 - Deformed Shape Plot for Thermoset Cylinder and End Cap

Figure 4 - Placing of 45 Degree Plies for Thermoset Blade Stiffened Cylinder

Figure 5 - Failure Predictions for Thermoset Blade Stiffened Cylinder

Buckling predictions : 186 to 215 bar (2718 to 3145 Psi)

Note : Based on Test Results from Brunswick Defense and Touchstone Labs.

Figure 6 - Inside of Cylinder with Strain Gages

Figure 7 - Post-Test Photo of Cylinder

Figure 8 - Close-Up of Failed End Bay Region and Wrinkle

Figure 9 - End Bay Overwrap Longitudinal Gage 101 Strain Plot

Figure 10 - Mid-Bay Interior Longitudinal Gage 227 Strain Plot

Figure 11 - Frame 1 Triaxial Gage 241 Longitudinal Leg Strain Plot

